

BEHAVIOUR OF CEMENTITIOUS MATRIX COMPOSITES UNDER DISPLACEMENT CONTROLLED CYCLIC LOADING

A G Magalhães¹, A T Marques¹, F Oliveira¹, P Soukatchoff², P T de Castro¹

¹ INEGI - Instituto de Engenharia Mecânica e Gestão Industrial, Portugal

² Centre de Recherches de Pont-a-Mousson, France

ABSTRACT

Under cyclic loading ruptures may occur at a stress lower than the maximum permissible for static loading. This phenomenon - fatigue - leads to rupture after a number of cycles if the stress amplitude is higher than the fatigue limit. The number of cycles until final rupture is composed of two phases: initiation of a defect and its propagation until final rupture. Fatigue rupture is a function of a large number of factors, such as surface quality, temperature, type and rate of loading, for example. They justify a large scatter and the need for a statistical characterization of the fatigue limit.

Some materials, such as concrete, do not display a fatigue limit, and their fatigue strength is conventionally defined at a given number of cycles such as 10^6 . For cementitious matrix composites, in the presence of sand and other aggregates, behaviour is markedly non-linear, and progressive growth of fissures substitutes catastrophic rupture. The slow growth is reinforced by the presence of fibres, which anchor the fissures, namely through the creation of fibre-bridges, subjecting fibres to a pull-out process whereby fibres break or are extracted from the matrix. Analysis of cyclic behaviour may be carried out quantifying the accumulated irreversible damage.

After developing a machine for displacement controlled cyclic testing, the authors studied the behaviour of cementitious matrix composites under this type of loading, particularly stress range and modulus as a function of number of cycles.

1. INTRODUCTION

In many situations a component may be subjected, in service, to dynamic loading, displaying less resistance than under static loading. This phenomenon, known as fatigue, is often described by curves of stress range versus number of cycles, and frequently an asymptotic behaviour defines the fatigue limit. Many metallic materials display a fatigue limit, but other materials, such as concrete, do not have that property in the usual sense. Therefore their resistance is defined for a given number of cycles - for example 10^6 [1]. For reinforced concrete, fatigue loaded for this number of cycles, the resistance will be of the order of 60 to 70% of the value for static loading.

The fatigue process consists on the successive accumulation of damage, inducing the loss of strength of the material. For homogeneous and isotropic materials the damage is associated to the initiation and propagation of a crack until final rupture occurs. For very heterogeneous materials, such as concrete, that concept of damage is meaningless, since, in this case, the simultaneous propagation of several cracks, together with the sliding and accommodation of the constituents is possible. This microstructural damage process may, eventually, not even lead to final rupture or to visible damage. When loaded under constant stress range, which correspond to the usual fatigue

testing, the great accommodation capacity leads to high displacement amplitudes, and this is often conducive to very unstable tests. When the cyclic loading consists of a constant displacement range, the initial force or stress range decreases with number of cycles; although this is not a conventional fatigue test leading to SN curves, the load or stress range drop is associated to the decrease in mechanical strength and to the accommodation of the fibre and matrix constituents.

2. OBJECTIVES

For given initial maximum and minimum values of load (or stress), and using constant displacement tests, the damage was measured as a function of number of cycles; the criterion for damage measurement was the load or stress range drop as a function of the number of cycles, for each initial load (stress) range. Measurements of number of cycles corresponding to 5, 10 and 20% drops were recorded. The experimental programme consisted of tests on several cementitious matrix composites, with glass fibre or metallic glass fibre reinforcements (FIBRAFLEX). As a complement to the damage assessment, and in the case of glass fibre reinforced materials, the elasticity modulus before and after tests consisting of 10^6 cycles was measured. All tests were performed with an initial value of $R=P_{\min}/P_{\max} = 0.1$.

3. EQUIPMENT DESIGNED FOR THIS TESTING PROGRAMME

A bending testing machine for displacement controlled tests was designed and built, Figure 1. It performs 3- or 4-point bend cyclic tests on beam specimens of rectangular cross section, at 10 Hz frequency. The specimen is supported by two load transducers of 2kN capacity, which may be displaced on a rectified table in order to set up the loading span. The displacement amplitude is set up using a cam consisting of eccentric rings; a bearing controls the actual loading device. The specimen is set up in the testing machine by lifting or descending the rectified table using a screw and wheel mechanism, [2].

Figure 1 - Displacement control fatigue machine

The loading sinusoid was defined from discrete data acquisition controlled by software. For the loading of Figure 2, for example, if a sufficiently large number of random data points is recorded, the evolution of the amplitude of the sinusoid during the test may be measured. For this purpose a sampling of some maximum and minimum values was recorded, and their averages recorded. Those mean values, and the corresponding time (or number of cycles) were recorded for subsequent treatment.

Figure 2 - Load amplitude acquisition

4. MATERIALS AND SPECIMENTS FOR THE TESTING PROGRAMME

The experimental programme concerned materials with two different reinforcements: glass fibre and metallic glass fibre (FIBRAFLEX FF 30L6). The specimens reinforced with glass fibre had nominal dimensions of 220x50x10 (mm³) and consisted of GRC(28), GRMC(28), PGRMM(28), GRC(84), GRMC(84), PGRMM(84), corresponding to three types of materials under two conditions:

GRC(28), Portland cement matrix with 5% weight of alkali resistant (AR) glass reinforcement with 38 mm length, 28 days of curing;

GRMC(28), Portland cement minerally modified with 5% weight of AR glass fibre of 38 mm length, 28 days of curing;

PGRMM(28), Portland cement minerally modified in association with 15% (weight) of an acrylic polymer, and reinforced with 5% (weight) of AR glass fibre, 28 days of curing;

GRC(84), GRMC(84), and PGRMM(84), materials as above, but with artificial ageing consisting of immersion in water at 50°C for 84 days.

The FIBRAFLEX fibre reinforced specimens had nominal dimensions 350x80x20(mm³). 4 different fiber weight percentages were tested: 0%, .4%, 1% and 1.6%. The fibres had length and width of 30mm and 1.6mm, respectively, and were randomly distributed in the matrix.

5. SECANT ELASTICITY MODULUS DROP IN THE GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED MATERIALS

The measurement of the fatigue loading dependence of the elasticity modulus was carried out on 3-point bend specimens tested before and after 10⁶ cycles, [3]. The modulus was defined for this purpose as the secant through the maximum stress level in the beginning of the test, Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Secant modulus

Temperature was 20°C and the specimens were supplied packed in plastic bags without any special conditioning. As auxiliary equipment an inductive LVDT transducer (RDP D5-200H) and a RDP ref. 7M signal conditioner were used. The data obtained for the 4 loadings corresponding to 5, 7, 10

and 12 MPa is presented in Figures 4 to 9. A comparative analysis of the drop in modulus for each case shows that artificially aged materials display a smaller reduction of secant modulus.

Figure 4 - GRC (28) modulus degradation in fatigue conditions

Figure 5 - GRC (84) modulus degradation in fatigue conditions

Figure 6 - GRMC (28) modulus degradation in fatigue conditions

Figure 7 - GRMC (84) modulus degradation in fatigue conditions

Figure 8 - PGRMM (28) modulus degradation in fatigue conditions

Figure 9 - PGRMM (84) modulus degradation in fatigue conditions

6. EVOLUTION OF MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM STRESS DURING CYCLIC LOADING FOR THE GLASS REINFORCED MATRICES.

The stress amplitude $\sigma_{\max}-\sigma_{\min}$ displays a rapid decrease in the beginning of the test, due to the accommodation of the matrix and reinforcements and converges to an asymptote after 200000 to 250000 cycles, as illustrated in Figure 10, where a logarithmic fit of the form

$$\Delta\sigma = a - b \log N \tag{1}$$

corresponding to the average of 5 tests at each stress level is presented.

Figure 10 - Stress amplitude versus number of cycles for GRC(28) material

A comparison of the behaviour of the several materials, in Figures 11 to 14, shows that the stress range drop is less noticeable in the case of the artificially aged materials. The GRMC and PGRMM composites presented a tendency for smaller drop during cyclic loading. This fact is particularly observed for the 5 and 12 MPa stress levels.

Figure 11 - Degradation for 5 MPa stress level

Figure 12 - Degradation for 7 MPa stress level

Figure 13 - Degradation for 10 MPa stress level

Figure 14 - Degradation for 12 MPa stress level

7. EVOLUTION OF THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM STRESS DURING CYCLIC LOADING FOR THE FIBRAFLEX RIBONS REINFORCED MATRICES

For each weight percentage reinforcement 4 levels of initial stress - 35, 45, 60, and 80% of rupture strength (as measured in a static test) were used. Generally, the stress range decreases very quickly, see Figure 15.

Figure 15 - Stress amplitude versus number of cycles for $V_f = 0.4\%$

For the initial maximum stress of 10 MPa, or greater, some ruptures during the test were observed, [4]. Figures 16 and 17 show two examples: propagation of a crack that goes around a large aggregate of the matrix, and the arrest of a crack near a fibre perpendicular to its path.

Figure 16 - Fatigue rupture around an aggregate

Figure 17 - Arrest of a crack near a fibre

In those cases where there was no rupture during the cyclic loading, consisting of 10^6 cycles, the range drop versus number of cycles of the FIBRAFLEX reinforced matrices was plotted, Figures 18 to 21.

Figure 18 - Degradation level for fibraflex material at 35% of MOR

Figure 19 - Degradation level for fibraflex material at 45% of MOR

Figure 20 - Degradation level for fibraflex material at 60% of MOR

Figure 21 - Degradation level for fibraflex material at 80% of MOR

A larger weight percentage of fibres in the matrix does not correspond to an improvement of the resistance to cyclic loading. This fact is more obvious for the greater stress levels. In this comparison it is shown that the composite with 0.4% fibre content displays the best overall performance as regards the drop in stress range during the test.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The testing programme carried out on glass fibre reinforced cementitious matrix composites leads to the following conclusions:

- considerable scatter was found, a situation to be expected when testing these materials,
- the materials do not display visible macroscopic damage when subjected to this type of loading,
- artificially aged materials suffer less damage (measured by the drop in stress range $\sigma_{max}-\sigma_{min}$) than corresponding non-aged materials,
- damage (measured by the drop in stress range $\sigma_{max}-\sigma_{min}$) occurs very quickly in the initial moments of the test,
- for all tests a *plateau* was found in the region 200000 to 250000 cycles, and corresponds to stress range drops of the order of, or greater than, 20%.

From the cyclic tests carried out on FIBRAFLEX ribbons reinforced cementitious matrix composites resulted the conclusions:

- scatter found for these tests was considerable,
- generally neither fatigue rupture nor visible damage was found,
- a large weight percentage of fibres degrades the cyclic loading resistance of these materials,
- of the materials tested, the 0.4% fibre weight percent displays the best overall performance as regards the drop in stress range during the test.

Acknowledgements

The work described was performed in the context of the project BRITE RI 1B 226 C (CD), coordinated by Centre de Recherches de Pont-a-Mousson, with BCA, ARMINES, SIGMA Beton, FORTON, INTRON and INEGI as partners. The authors acknowledge the contribution of the Commission of the European Communities for this project.

References

1. Chang, D.I., Chai, W.K., *A study of the fatigue behaviour of reinforced concrete structures*, International Journal of Pressure Vessels and Piping, vol.40, pp51-75, 1989
2. Magalhães, A.G., *Caracterização do comportamento mecânico de compósitos de matriz cimentosa* (in Portuguese), MSc thesis, Universidade do Porto, 1990
3. Magalhães, A.G., Marques, A.T., Oliveira, F., Castro, P.T., Final report of INEGI for the BRITE project RI 1B 226, Oct 1991
4. Magalhães, A.G., Marques, A.T., Oliveira, F., Castro, P.T., Addendum to final report of INEGI for the BRITE project RI 1B 226, 1992